

PADNET: A PATCH-BASED ANOMALY DETECTION FRAMEWORK FOR INDUSTRIAL PIPELINE DAMAGE DETECTION

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ABSTRACT

Traditional industrial infrastructure maintenance methods often rely on manual inspection, which can be time-consuming and prone to errors. Anomaly detection can play a crucial role in automated industrial infrastructure damage inspection, e.g. pipeline installations. This pipeline damage detection approach is based on the fact that damages are few and can be considered anomalies (essentially outliers) in an extensive industrial pipeline installation, like the ones found in chemical industries or oil refineries. This paper proposes a novel patch-based Anomaly Detection Network, that employs deep learning for detecting insulated pipe damages. It consists of three main components: a) a pipeline segmentation module, b) an image patch proposal module, and c) an anomaly detection module. These components work sequentially first to localize insulated pipelines in the input UAV or ground camera images or video frames and then analyze image patches to detect and localize any damages. Importantly, the anomaly detection module can be trained using undamaged pipeline image data only, hence eliminating the need for costly damaged pipeline image annotation. Experimental results demonstrate PADNet effectiveness in detecting pipeline damages, making it a promising solution for autonomous industrial infrastructure inspection.

Index Terms— Insulated Pipe Damage Detection, Anomaly Detection, Autoencoders, Computer Vision, Deep Learning

1. INTRODUCTION

Automated detection of anomalies, particularly in industrial installations, is vital for reducing human workload and ensuring safety by preventing accidents. Manual or automated visual inspection, e.g. using drones, can be used to this end. Visual anomaly detection is a critical computer vision task, for identifying of unusual or abnormal patterns, structures, or objects within images. The objective is to distinguish anomalous image patches from a set of "normal" ones. It is often formulated as a one-class classification problem [1], since abnormal data can be considered as outliers that deviate from the normal image data probability distribution.

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Automated anomaly detection holds great promise for industrial inspection applications, such as detecting pipeline damages [2]. This problem naturally aligns with anomaly detection principles, as damaged pipeline sections e.g., having torn insulations, insulation holes, or pipeline leaks, are rare, compared to undamaged ones.

Traditional pipeline damage detection approaches often rely on Deep Neural Networks (DNNs), such as YOLO detectors [3], Support Vector Machines (SVMs) [4] or Decision Trees [5] that are trained through supervised learning. However, these methods necessitate large annotated pipeline image datasets, which are costly and time-consuming to acquire, especially when the anomaly types and morphologies are multifaceted or even unknown.

To address these challenges, anomaly detection-based approaches have emerged for pipeline damage detection in the form of one-class classification [6], autoencoders [7], or generative models [8]. While these methods have shown promise on some rather limited benchmark datasets, they face limitations when applied to real-world industrial pipeline installations, particularly in dealing with background image clutter and noise.

In this paper, we present a novel CNN-based framework for automated industrial pipeline damage detection. It comprises three sequential modules: a pre-trained image segmentation module for pipeline region segmentation, an image patch proposal module for selecting pipeline patches (regions of interest), and a visual (image) anomaly detection module based on autoencoder DNNs for pipeline damage detection. Importantly, the image patch autoencoder is trained using a simple yet effective anomaly detection technique, requiring only image patch data from undamaged pipes, thereby eliminating the need for collecting annotated image data from damaged pipeline sections. Due to its patch-based approach, the proposed pipeline damage detection method faces two other main challenges, namely pipeline viewpoint variability, camera angle and observation point variability, and tiny object detection difficulties because most pipeline image abnormalities cover a very small pixel area of the entire pipeline image. Experimental results in real-world industrial pipeline installations demonstrate the efficacy of the proposed PADNet framework.

2. RELATED WORK

2.1. Anomaly Detection

While classical DNN-based object detection methods, such as Yolov5 [9] and Yolo-Nas [10] are applicable to pipeline damage detection, their reliance on labeled image data (i.e., damage-bounding boxes) poses practical challenges, due to the scarcity of annotated pipeline damage images. This limitation underscores the importance of exploring unsupervised anomaly detection techniques that can effectively identify irregularities in pipeline images, without recording to extensive data labeling.

Pipeline damage detection approaches range from traditional statistical methods [11] to advanced machine learning techniques [12]. Statistical methods relying on data location and dispersion measures, such as sample mean and standard deviation, while simple, struggle to capture high-dimensional image data complexity. Supervised learning techniques [13] demonstrate effectiveness by employing, but face challenges in acquiring diverse labeled data and adapting to evolving pipeline or damage characteristics and/or diversity. Unsupervised learning methods [14], including clustering algorithms like k-means and hierarchical clustering, along with innovative neural network architectures like autoencoders, excel in scenarios where labeled data are scarce or difficult to obtain. They group similar pipeline image data settings, identify outliers, and recognize different types of damages, structural differences in pipes, and industrial environment damages, without needing a priori labeled training data.

However, unsupervised learning, such as One-Class Support Vector Machines (OC-SVM) [15], encounters difficulties in distinguishing subtle anomalies amidst noisy industrial pipeline image datasets. Semi-supervised learning [16] offers a middle ground by leveraging both labeled and unlabeled data through techniques, such as self-training and co-training. Its success relies on the assumption that labeled examples accurately represent the diversity of potential pipeline image data anomalies.

Deep learning methods, particularly autoencoders, such as Convolutional Autoencoders (CAEs) [17] or Variational Autoencoders (VAEs) [7], have shown promise in learning complex image data representations. They detect image anomalies by reconstructing input data and identifying disparities between the reconstructed and input images. Unlike supervised approaches, they can also detect any form of anomaly, without focusing on specific pipeline image data types. Alternative approaches include using structural similarity indices, adversarial training, and iterative projection methods.

2.2. Industrial Pipeline Damage Detection

Imaging technologies [18, 19] have been increasingly utilized for anomaly detection in industrial pipelines. These

approaches offer a non-intrusive means of monitoring vast pipeline installations using ground or drone camera imagery. Computer vision algorithms can identify visual signs of pipeline damages, such as leaks or structural deformities. Factors like image resolution varying illumination and weather conditions influence the effectiveness of these methods.

Machine learning and statistical analysis algorithms [20, 21] can be used to enhance the detection on pipeline anomaly accuracy and reliability. Although the approaches outlined in the previous subsection are used for image anomaly detection, they have not been implemented in industrial inspection applications. In pipeline damage detection tasks, algorithms such as the Local Outlier Factor (LOF) were used in conjunction with neural feature extractors DNN models, such as VGG16 [22] and ResNet50 [23]. Nonetheless, they confront interpretability issues, are DNN hyperparameter sensitive, and may run overfitting risks. Earlier studies addressed these difficulties, by utilizing teacher-student frameworks that were combined with feature extractors, such as the STFPM [24]. However, these approaches face challenges in effectively transferring knowledge between teacher and student DNN networks. To this end, then optimize DNN feature-matching across multiple scales, and carefully tune DNN hyperparameters to ensure optimal performance in anomaly detection tasks. Finally, patch-based approaches address the same issues, by introducing PaDim [25] and Patch-SVDD [26], which are suitable for industrial applications. Although they can focus on specific image regions and can catch dynamically complex image patterns, they may struggle to reliably collect contextual information beyond the image patch boundaries, and they risk missing image anomalies that span neighboring image patches. Additionally, these methods may face scalability issues when dealing with large image datasets.

This paper proposes a novel framework based on anomaly detection techniques that are explicitly tailored for industrial pipeline damage detection. The method leverages the strengths of autoencoders while addressing domain-specific considerations to enhance image anomaly detection robustness and effectiveness.

3. PROPOSED PADNET METHODOLOGY

This paper introduces an end-to-end CNN-based framework for efficient real-world industrial pipeline damage detection from RGB images. It comprises three modules, a) a pipe segmentation module, b) an image patch proposal module, and c) a visual detection module, that operates in a novel configuration, which allows the accurate detection of unknown type pipeline damages in real-world industrial environments, as it is illustrated in Figure 1.

3.1. Pipe Segmentation

The first step of the proposed framework comprises a pipeline image segmentation DNN that sequents pipeline image regions [27]. It sequents input RGB image $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N \times 3}$ to produce the pipeline segmentation mask $\mathbf{S} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N}$. This meticulous DNN region segmentation process enables the extraction of detailed 2D spatial pipeline region information that is crucial for the patch-based image analysis and visual anomaly detection modules, as it allows the subsequent PAD-Net modules to focus only on the pipeline image regions and to filter out noisy image regions, such as cluttered image background.

3.2. Image Patch Proposal

After extracting the binary pipe segmentation map, both the RGB input image $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N \times 3}$ of height M and width N pixels, and its predicted segmentation mask \mathbf{S} are fed to the second step of the proposed framework, the image patch proposal module, denoted as P . The goal of the image patch proposal module is to extract non-overlapping image patches of size $p_1 \times p_2$ each, that correspond only to pipeline image regions so that they can be fed to the visual damage detection module. To this end, the extracted pipeline segmentation mask \mathbf{S} masks out the background regions from \mathbf{X} , thus producing $\tilde{\mathbf{X}} = \mathbf{X} \odot \mathbf{S}$, $\tilde{\mathbf{X}} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N \times 3}$.

Since the input images, \mathbf{X} may be captured in a wide range of illumination conditions or may correspond to many different pipe types, the related image region patches may also have large differences in brightness, which could affect the visual pipeline damage detection performance. To tackle this issue, the image patch proposal module applies histogram equalization [28] in the segmented input image $\tilde{\mathbf{X}}$ before calculating image patches. An example of the patch proposal process can be seen in Fig. 1. Since histogram equalization improves the contrast and the overall quality of the input image by distributing intensity values uniformly, it is ensured that details in both high and low-intensity regions are visible in the obtained patches, thus enhancing the visibility of features that might have been previously obscured. Overall, this process aims to facilitate damage detection performed in the final step in different real-world scenarios.

So, then, $\hat{\mathbf{X}}$ which is the histogram-equalized image is split into a set \mathcal{P} of image patches that contains a number of image patches $\mathbf{P}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{p_1 \times p_2 \times 3}$, $i = 1, \dots, K$, where p_1, p_2 are the patch height and patch width, respectively. The number K of the image patches in the set \mathcal{P} depends on the segmentation mask extracted in the first step and thus can change dynamically for each input image. The full pipeline of the image patch proposal module can be formulated as:

$$\mathcal{P} = \{g(x_i, s_i) : x_i \in \hat{\mathbf{X}}, s_i \in \mathbf{S}\} = \text{split}(\hat{\mathbf{X}}), \quad (1)$$

where $\text{split}()$ is the function that splits the masked image $\tilde{\mathbf{X}}$ into patches by calculating the corresponding vectors $\mathbf{p}_i =$

$[p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4]^T$, where p_1, \dots, p_4 represent the pixel coordinates of the top-left and bottom-right corners of the patch in the original image \mathbf{X} .

3.3. Visual Pipeline Anomaly Detection

The visual damage detection module employs a CNN autoencoder. Its encoder maps the input image patch data \mathbf{P}_i into lower-dimensional latent space representations z_i , while the decoder reconstructs the input image patch data $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_i$ from this latent space representation.

During autoencoder training, it aims at minimizing the reconstruction error between the input patch \mathbf{P}_i and its reconstruction $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_i$, such as the Mean Squared Error (MSE). In addition to MSE, other similarity metrics like Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) or Cosine Similarity (COSSIM) can also be employed to measure the similarity/ dissimilarity between \mathbf{P}_i and $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_i$. These metrics offer different perspectives on the quality of reconstruction and can be utilized based on the specific characteristics of the input data and the desired sensitivity to anomalies.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

4.1. Datasets

To evaluate the proposed method for real-world insulated pipe damage detection, two RGB picture datasets were collected and manually annotated.

The Oil Refinery pipeline dataset contains a variety of RGB images of functioning insulated pipes captured at varying angles and featuring different pipe quantities within each frame. All images depict industrial (oil refinery) pipeline installations at image resolutions ranging from 1920×1080 to 4032×3024 . Overall, the dataset comprises 1k RGB images, which leads to 45000 image patches, 35000 normal, and 10000 abnormal ones. The normal image patches contain undamaged pipe regions that are only used for training purposes.

The AUTH pipeline dataset consists of 77 RGB images having resolution 1920×1080 pixels. They have been specifically designated for evaluating the damage detection performance of the proposed PADNet framework. Example samples from the AUTH pipe dataset are shown in Fig. 2. The image proposal module extracted 7745 image patches, out of the 77 images: 4850 were normal pipeline image patches and 2895 were abnormal ones, corresponding to pipeline damages.

4.2. Implementation Details

First, an image-based visual anomaly detection approach (PADNetv1) has been implemented using the entire RGB pipeline images. Then a patch-based visual Anomaly Detection approach (PADNetv2) operates on the entire image patches without image background segmentation. Finally, the

Fig. 1. Overall PADNet framework architecture.

Fig. 2. Example images from the AUTH pipeline image dataset.

third version (PADNetv3) operates on only pipeline image region patches.

The utilized autoencoder architecture employed in the anomaly detection modules, PADNetv2 and PADNetv3 accepts RGB image patches of size 64×64 pixels. Its encoder part comprises two convolutional layers with 32 and 64 filters, respectively, each followed by max-pooling layers. The decoder part comprises three convolutional layers with 8 and 16 filters, each followed by upsampling layers. Finally, the decoder has a convolutional layer with 3 filters, a 3×3 kernel, sigmoid activation, and the same padding for output \hat{P}_i .

The RGB input image patches are trained for 100 epochs with batch size 32 and a learning rate of 0.001, utilizing the Adam optimizer for efficient optimization. It is worth noting that, during training, the autoencoder is trained only with 3500 normal pipeline image patches. Then, it is tested in both normal and abnormal ones, which came out from images from the Refinery image dataset. In total 18850 unlabeled test image patches were used that came out from 300 images of the Refinery dataset and 77 images from AUTH dataset.

Table 1. Results from image-based AD (PADNetv1), patch-based AD with background information (PADNetv2), patch-based AD without background information (PADNetv3) approaches using the anomaly detection module of the proposed system (PADNet) on the AUTH dataset.

Model	Precision	Recall	F1 score	AUROC
PADNetv1	0.463	0.873	0.605	0.735
PADNetv2	0.512	0.851	0.639	0.773
PADNetv3	0.623	0.927	0.746	0.898

Table 2. Results from the patch-based pipeline damage detection models on the AUTH dataset.

Model	Precision	Recall	F1 score	AUROC
Yolov5 [9]	0.333	0.714	0.455	0.523
Yolo-Nas [10]	0.519	0.822	0.636	0.671
VGG16-LOF [22]	0.532	0.638	0.579	0.545
ResNet50-LOF [23]	0.611	0.636	0.623	0.604
OC-SVM [15]	0.515	0.891	0.653	0.703
STFPM [24]	0.613	0.845	0.710	0.739
PaDiM [25]	0.621	0.869	0.724	0.745
Patch SVDD [26]	0.615	0.923	0.738	0.867
PADNetv3 (Ours)	0.623	0.927	0.746	0.898

4.3. Evaluation Results

After the autoencoder training procedure, the proposed PADNet are tested with different loss function metrics to find out which gives a better prediction of pipe damage in the image patches provided. MSE, SSIM, and COSSIM reconstruction errors are used for anomaly detection. Afterward, the threshold value of 0.015, determined through a grid search based on the training loss, was applied to the reconstruction errors to classify patches as normal or abnormal (damaged ones). PADNet was meticulously evaluated using Precision, Recall, F1 score, and Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristics (AUROC) metrics, as shown in Table 1.

PADNetv3 outperformed the other two PADNet versions. This proves that the best approach for visual pipeline anomaly detection task employs clear pipeline image patches without any image background information. The MSE yields superior results in terms of precision and recall metrics vs SSIM or COSSIM error metrics.

The proposed method PADNetv3 was also compared to eight competitors: Yolov5 [9], Yolo-Nas [10], VGG16-LOF [22], ResNet50-LOF [23], OC-SVM [15], STFPM [24], PaDiM [25] and Patch SVDD [26]. They are tested in the AUTH pipe dataset that contains 77 images with two basic types of damage: holes and open insulations.

The results of these methods are reported in Table 2. for a 64×64 input patch resolution. The proposed PADNetv3 method exhibits a significant performance advantage over all other eight competing methods.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper presents PADNetv3, a deep learning-based framework for unsupervised anomaly detection in industrial pipeline images. The proposed methodology leverages a pipeline segmentation module, an image patch proposal module, and an autoencoder-based anomaly detection module to identify and localize pipeline damages. The advantage is that it can employ only normal image samples for autoencoder training.

The experimental results on a diverse dataset highlight the effectiveness of the proposed framework in pipeline anomaly detection and its superior performance against eight baseline competitors. The proposed model demonstrates high precision, recall, F1 score, and AUROC showcasing its potential for real-world applications in industrial inspection.

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6. REFERENCES

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